

**Isolation and Identification of Fungi Causing Disease to Some Common
Vegetables found in Akola region**

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Abstract:

Fungal infections are a common cause of vegetable degeneration. These infections can strike plants either before or after harvest, Various types of vegetables are grown worldwide and are consumed by human for nutrition in terms of bioactive nutrient molecules such as dietary fiber, vitamins and minerals, The results indicated that the primary cause of infection in the vegetables under investigation was Deuteromycetean fungi. Members from orders Moniliales are Fusarium, Curvularia, Bipolaris, Trichoderma, Pithomyces causes severe diseases where as members from order Mucorales such as Mucor and Rhizopus are found on maximum vegetables. Mucor and Rhizopus are found on maximum vegetables. Aspergillus the member of order Aspergillales was also found on some vegetables.

Key words: *Curvularia, Bipolaris, Trichoderma, Pithomyces, vegetables etc.*

Introduction

Fungal infections are a common cause of vegetable degeneration. These infections can strike plants either before or after harvest. Fungi-contaminated produce is no longer fit for sale or consumption. These infections may begin as superficial wounds, which are often caused by forceful trauma. Despite their susceptibility to fungal and bacterial infections, vegetables are a valuable source of income, as well as a sustainable food supply and nutritional security.

Besides, many fungal diseases may be controlled if detected and correctly identified in a timely manner. Thus, early detection of fungal pathogens associated with vegetables crops become important in plant health monitoring. This may help to manage disease infections in different stages of development, minimizing the risk of disease spreading and avoiding the introduction of new ones (Brasier, 2008). known as parasitic fungi, infect all plants. These fungi create indicators on the surface of their hosts, including mycelium, sclerotia, sporophores, fruiting bodies, and spores. Symptoms are merely the outward manifestation of the diseased plant or plant tissue; signs are different.

It is crucial to survey fungal infections on readily available vegetables in the area since doing so protects the public's health by highlighting potential dangers related to eating contaminated produce. By revealing the kinds and abundance of fungi that damage vegetables production, these surveys help safeguard agricultural products. Farmers' decision-making processes can be influenced by their understanding of the economic consequences of these illnesses, which can result in the application of efficient control methods. This research may create novel approaches to controlling fungal infections and enhancing fruit quality benefits from the use of survey data.

Material and methods:

Throughout February and Matvh 2025, a routine survey was conducted for gather Contaminated vegetables from various location of Akola. Samples were collected from nearby markets such as Janata, Jatharpeth, Ramdaspath and New Tapdiya Nagar

Isolation of fungi: After collection infected vegetables, They were identified using Flora of Marathwada by Naik, they were washed with water to get rid of any remaining dust. Their symptoms were noted. Cutting a tiny piece of the unhealthy area of the vegetables together with the healthy portion allowed for isolation. These parts were placed aseptically into sterilized slants made of potato dextrose agar (potato peeling 200g/20 gm potato powder, dextrose 20g, agar 15g, and distilled water 1000 ml) in petri dishes that were kept at 25 -27°C (+ 2). The surfaces of these parts were sterilized with 90% alcohol.

Identification of fungi:

Morphological identification of the fungal strains is based on the morphology of the fungal culture colony, size, colour, characteristics of the spores or hyphae and reproductive structure were examined critically with reference to mycological texts. (H. L. Barnett & Barry B.Hunter, 1972). In some cases the infected tissues were stained by cotton blue and lactophenol (Mc Lean et.al., 1965) and observed under the microscope. After 7 days fungal colonies were recognized according to microscopic features and classed on many keys and references.

Observation and Results:

Symptomology & isolation of fungi-

Table 1

Sr.No.	Name of vegetables	Symptoms Caused and fungi	Name of Fungi
1. B)	Solanum lycopersicum L. Solanaceae	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The infected area of the fruit become soft and mushy or the fungus breaks down the tissue.• Infected areas appears water, soaked, and the colour darken after turning brown.• As it deteriorates, it emits a strong unpleasant odor due to the metabolic activities of the fungi.	Mucor sp., Bipolaris sp.,

2. D)	Brassica oleracea var. botrytis. / Brassicaceae	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Fungal infections after lead to the decay of plant tissue, resulting in soft, mushy spots on the surface on unripe inflorescence.• Infected ares shows discoloration, such as darkening or browning.• In some cases, infected areas dry out or shrivel, especially if the infection progresses.• Fungal infections can disrupt normal inflorescence development, leading to malformed or misshapen.• As the infection progress and decays it may emit a foul odour.	Mucor sp., Fusarium sp.,
3. E)	Solanum tuberosum L. Solanaceae	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• It produce visible mold growth on the surface of the tuber, appearing as fuzzy patches of different colors such as brown, green, black.• These fungi can affect tuber which become soft and mushy, leading to decay and ultimately rotting of the affected areas.• The affected areas of the tuber exhibit discoloration, appearing darker or discoloured compared to healthy parts of the tuber.• Fungal infections accelerate the deterioration of tuber, leading to a shorter shelf life and making them unsuitable for consumption.	Phoma sp., Mucor sp., Aspergillus sp.
4. H)	Ipomoea batatas L. Convolvulaceae	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The infected portion of the fruit becomes soft and mushy, indicating decay.• The infected area darken to change colour, often becoming darker brown or black.• The infected area exhibit discoloration typically turning darker brown or block.	Mucor Sp., Aspergillus sp.,

Taxonomical studies of the Isolates.

1) Aspergillus sp. Morphology of isolate: The colonies were white at first, but hyaline branch septate quickly turned black. The septate hyaline conidiophores unbranched and ended in globose vesicles. Sterigmata flask shaped produce conidia in a chain in an acropetal succession. (See photoplate-8C)

2) Rhizopus sp. Morphology of isolate: Hyphae filamentous, branching, colonies develop. The production of sporangiophores took place within a spherical structure called a sporangium, which is held up by a large apophyte columella at the top. (See photoplate- 8D)

3) Fusarium sp. Morphology of isolate: Conidiophores vary in length and branching pattern, conidia are hyaline, microconidia are formed in simple, unbranched chains, macroconidia fragile, awle shaped, and taper towards both ends. The mycelium is septate, cottony, and somewhat pink in culture.

5) Mucor sp. Morphology of isolate: A column shaped columella supports and elevates the apical, globular sporangia formed by simple or branching sporangiophores, which are fast growing, usually white to beige or gray colonies.

5) *Trichoderma* sp. Morphology of isolate: Conidia hyaline, ovoid, single celled, and borne in small terminal clusters, are easily recognized by their quick growth and green patches or cushions of conidia. Hyaline conidiophores are highly branching and not verticillate, while phialides might be

Infected Vegetables collected from different locality of Akola

1. *Solanum lycopersicum* L.

2. *Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis* L.

3. *Solanum tuberosum* L. 2

4. *Ipomoea batatas* L. 2

Photo plate 2- Growth of Fungus/Bacteria of Infected vegetables

1. *Solanum lycopersicum* L.

2. *Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis* L.

3. *Solanum tuberosum* L.

Taxonomical studies of the Isolates.

1) *Aspergillus* sp.

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5) *Trichoderma* sp. Morphology of isolate:

Conidia hyaline, ovoid, single celled, and borne in small terminal clusters, are easily recognized by their quick growth and green patches or cushions of conidia. Hyaline conidiophores are highly branching and not verticillate, while phialides might be single or in groups.

Discussion

An investigation was carried out on locally grown veggies growing in the Akola that contaminated with fungus. *Solanum melongena*, *Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis*, *Dolichos Solanum tuberosum*, *Spinacia oleracea* and *Allium cepa* were the veggies chosen for the lablab var. *lignosus*, *Praecitrullus fistulosus*, *Lagenaria siceraria*, *Solanum lycopersicum* current survey.

The results indicated that the primary cause of infection in the vegetables under investigation was Deuteromycetean fungi. Members from orders Moniliales are *Fusarium*, *Curvularia*, *Bipolaris*, *Trichoderma*, *Pithomyces* causes savior diseases where as members from order Mucorales such as *Mucor* and *Rhizopus* are found on maximum vegetables. *Aspergillus* the member of order Aspergillales was also found on some vegetables. It was discovered that *Mucor*, a Zygomycete member, was the prevalent fungus responsible for infections in all vegetables which were examined. It was discovered that *Bipolaris* sp. and *Trichoderma* sp. only infected one host.

The ability of Deuteromycetean fungus to collect nourishment from various host is demonstrated by the presence of the same fungi on diverse plants. These fungi can therefore spread quickly to new hosts and have a better chance of surviving as a result.

Species of *Mucor* found on *Solanum lycopersicum* L., *Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis* L., *Solanum tuberosum* L., *Ipomoea batatas* L., *Allium cepa* L., *Solanum melongena* L.

Species of *Fusarium* was found on *Brassica oleracea* var. *botrytis* L., *Praecitrullus fistulosus* (stock) Pangalo L., *Solanum melongena* L.

Species of *Rhizopus* was found on *Praecitrullus fistulosus* (stock) Pangalo L.

Species of *Aspergillus* was found on *Solanum tuberosum* L., *Praecitrullus fistulosus* (stock) pangalo L., *Ipomoea batatas* L.

Species of *Trichoderma* Sp., was found on *Allium cepa* L. Species of *Bipolaris* was found on *Solanum lycopersicum* L.

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